

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE INCOME OF HIGHER EDUCATION

Karlibaeva G.

Independent researcher of Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract

In the article, the composition and sources of funding of educational institutions from the budget, the process of financial planning and forecasting, the principles of financing higher education, as well as the mechanism of financial support of higher education in the context of state financing and the formation of a socially oriented market economy. It is used to achieve the main goals of its activity.

Keywords: higher education, innovation, financing system.

Introduction

The income of universities has undergone significant changes in the modern economy: there has been a transition from full budget financing of universities to the formation of a state function, increasing the share of their own income. Modern universities use different sources of funding, so there is a need to analyze the composition of income and manage it.

The authors' analysis of university income showed that universities with a traditional income structure with a high share of paid education services are at increased risk of financial sustainability and losing their human resources. The main mechanism for reducing risks is income diversification and management of their structure.

Consider the concept of income of the educational organization and the available classifications. Income can be defined from economic, legal and accounting points of view.

Theoretical aspects of research.

From an economic point of view, income is "funds received as a result of any activity in the form of money and other values". From a legal point of view, "income is an economic benefit in cash or in kind, if it can be estimated and taken into account to the extent that such benefit can be estimated[1]." The legal interpretation of income is based on the concepts of property rights, property and obligations.

The definition of income accounting is based on the synthesis of economic and legal interpretations and reveals the methods of accounting for income and presenting information about them in the financial statements of the enterprise: "the income of the organization is recognized as an increase in economic profit as a result of the participants (property with the exception of owners') contributions, receiving assets (money, other property) and (or) paying liabilities that lead to an increase in the capital of this organization.

Thus, income is a cash flow generated as a result of the implementation of various types of economic activity, which constitutes the profit of an economic entity and ensures its financial stability[2]. The income of educational organizations has its own characteristics determined by the scope of economic activity. The income category of the educational organization includes the inflow of funds, the simultaneous occurrence of obligations for the provision of educational services, scientific and research activities that determine the financial result of the organization's activities[3].

The main groups that determine the nature of the activities of educational organizations, their financial results and possible tax consequences include the following[4]:

- main activity: training one or more educational programs, content, students;
- conducting research;
- activities to ensure and provide service to the educational and scientific-research process;
- other activities, including other incomes: other activities allowed to educational organizations that generate income and are not related to the specified types of main activities.

The role and importance of university income is determined by the sources and types of income. A large number of income classifications are given in the scientific literature, and their broad, all-encompassing nature should be emphasized. In our opinion, the classification of university income should reflect the content of the activities of educational organizations.

It is necessary to pay attention to the types of income that affect the strategy of the university in the educational services market. It is important which categories of consumers finance educational services. For example, the involvement of third-party employers in the financing of educational services (co-financing) guarantees the student's employment after graduation, which has a positive effect on the university's rating on graduate employability.

Foreign aspects of research.

In modern conditions, it is important to distinguish this type of income as funds from foreign sources - in this case, an indirect assessment of the competitiveness of universities in the international market of educational services is provided, this indicator, as a rule, is included in various university ratings and the efficiency of universities indirectly affects monitoring indicators. The income from research and innovation activity indicates the involvement of scientific staff in the regional economic activity, which serves to attract students to research and development activities and develop relations with potential employers[5].

One of the sources of income is funding from the budget for the implementation of state tasks. The institution's success in the educational market and research activities will affect the size of this assignment and increase the likelihood of increasing this funding in the form of subsidies[6][7]. Currently, higher education institutions are entering the competition for the quality and volume of the state assignment, which does not

stand behind the competition in the market of paid educational services.

The composition of revenues has a significant impact on the risks of the economic activity of universities, first of all, there is a risk that "the budget itself does not correspond to the reality of the market in the composition of its revenues." Examining university income only by sources, budget financing and distribution of universities' own income, as is customary in modern research and regulatory documents, does not reflect the potential of the university, does not show convergence, the main component of the university's activity. educational, scientific and, most importantly, innovative today, that is. industrial character, activity.

Analysis and result of research.

Today, universities are unable to provide the high growth in paid admissions that students need for their development, which further exacerbates the poor demographic situation. Tuition costs are rising faster than prices. A number of factors have led to a decrease in the profitability of paid education, and in some areas to unprofitability.

Thus, the dominance of paid educational services as the only source of income increases the risk of educational organizations. In order to restore profitability, universities face the task of diversifying the income structure, focusing on increasing the share of income from scientific and innovative activities up to 20 percent.

Taking into account the directions of income diversification, the following measures can be proposed[8]:

- To promote the results of research activities of the university and to increase the share of income from research, to create a marketing structure for the coordination of commercial projects of the university, while the research work should be based on the project approach oriented to the market of the final product. and services.

- the second direction of income diversification is the formation of targeted funds for the development of the university.

In addition to the income discussed in this article, the expenses of educational organizations play a major role in ensuring the financial stability of an educational organization.

Today's difficult economic conditions give special importance to the development of higher education institutions using new models of revenue management, which will not only survive, but also meet the new requirements of the educational services market. maintaining labor market, competitiveness and financial stability. This requires universities to look for new solutions for revenue management.

In modern conditions, there is a clear lack of budget funds and, therefore, an active search for alternative sources of financing, which is especially characteristic of higher education institutions. Forms of innovation as the main type of income-generating activity in higher education: parks (scientific, scientific, technological, production), business incubators, innovation centers and clusters are also little studied.

There are different legal approaches to the qualification of innovative activities of educational organizations from the point of view of legal documents on education and legal documents regulating innovative activities.

Legal conflicts that arise in the application of the current legal norms on the lease of federal real estate given to higher education institutions indicate the need to reform the current legislation to regulate legal relations arising from the use of federal property.

Possible limits on the use of funds from income-generating activities, as well as possible restrictions on the procedure for their use, remain unclear.

Conclusion.

Based on the above, the current methods and methods of state control (control) over the spending of funds from income-generating activities of educational organizations, including the less studied type of control such as public control, are of scientific interest. .

These cases show the relevance of research aimed at formalizing the legal conditions for the emergence of income-generating activity, determining its legal essence;

- to carry out a comparative analysis of regulatory legal documents regulating the income-generating activities of higher education institutions;

- to distinguish the concepts related to the concept of "income generating activity"; development of proposals on improving the legal norms regulating the income-generating activities of educational institutions in the educational system.

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